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Research Article

**STRESS HYPERGLYCEMIA IN ACUTE CORONARY
SYNDROME: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY****Dr. Amna Tariq, Dr. Maryam Liaqat, Dr. Muhammad Noman Khalid**

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Abstract:

Objectives: The aim of the study was to determine the stress hyperglycemia in patients of ACS.

Methods: The number of intense Coronary syndrome cases enrolled for our research was one hundred. Researcher chose all men and women having age in between forty to seventy years among one hundred cases from Department of Cardiology at Mayo Hospital Lahore from March 2018 to August 2018. Researcher evaluated stress hyperglycemia in all registered cases for research.

Results: The age of entire cases in our study was in between fifty-one to sixty-nine years. The number of patients diagnosed with stress hyperglycemia while hospitalization was thirty-nine (thirty-nine percent) as well as the number of cases died during treatment in hospital was twelve (12 percent). The researcher identified statistically important (P value is equal to 0.056) linkage during hospitalization causalities and stress hyperglycemia.

Conclusion: The finding of our research presented by the researcher, identified many ACS cases with stress hyperglycemia. During hospitalization, researcher found a strong connection in between casualities and stress hyperglycemia.

Key Words: Mortality, acute myocardial infarction (AMI), stratification, acute coronary syndrome (ACS), stress hyperglycemia (SH).

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INTRODUCTION:

A huge number of researches conducted earlier have confirmed that during hospitalization hyperglycemia is casual in ACS cases as well as it is a huge hazardous element for mortality along with hospitalization diversities. Whereas the precise categorization of hyperglycemia has not been constituting, the ascendancy of acknowledging hyperglycemia in earlier conducted research concerning to epidemic ranges from twenty-five percent to greater than fifty percent of cases hospitalized with ACS. In a meta scrutiny of fifteen comparatively short and largely older research analyzed the linkage between entrance of glucose level along with demise, capes et al presented the hazard of hospitalizing demise in those cases who are victimized by diabetic with AMI and admission glucose is greater than 110mg/dl was 3.9 correlate with nondiabetic AMI cases who were standard glyemic.

All victimized diabetic cases with AMI and admission glucose are greater than 180mg/dl had a seventy percent of the great hazard of hospitalizing casualty correlate with those diabetic affected cases who have common admission glucose limits. Uniformly, Foo et al presented a smooth association among huge intake of glucose level along with the larger percentage of left ventricular collapse and casualties due to heart problems in twenty-one hundred and twenty-seven cases with ACS. Meier et al also presented greater extended term casualty rate and huge infarct magnitude (calculated by creatine kinase as well as MB-fraction levels) in hyperglycemic AMI cases together with diabetes as well as in the absence of diabetes. The research of Wahab et along with standers et al also proposed that admission hyperglycemia connected hazard is much greater in AMI cases in the absence of formerly known diabetes. Our research objective was to analyze the regularity of stress hyperglycemia in ACS cases and its connection with the hospitalized casualty. The finding of the research may lead us to the qualitative treatment of acute coronary syndrome patients and to curtail the ratio of casualty along with complications concerning it.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The number of intense Coronary syndrome cases enrolled for our research was one hundred.

Researcher chose all men and women having age in between forty to seventy years among one hundred cases from Department of Cardiology at Mayo Hospital Lahore March 2018 to August 2018. Researcher takes written consent from the guardians of all cases along with organizational review committee. The researcher conducted clinical checkup as well as blood sampling of entire cases and dispatch to the laboratory for glucose examination. Researcher writes the result of glucose examination on Performa fabricated for said purpose as well as on statistical profile of the victim. All those cases having glucose range greater than or equal to 140mg/dl at hospitalization time was marked as victims of stress hyperglycemia.

Researcher feed entire composed data into of SPSS along with evaluation. Researcher measured SD and average for age as well as repetition counting for the purpose of identifying the patient for stress hyperglycemia, to find out hospitalized death or not, as well as gender. The researcher conducted stratification in association with the hospitalized casualty. Researcher performed Chi-square test to check the relation in hospitalized deaths and stress hyperglycemia. P. value is less than or equal to 0.05 was assumed as statistically important.

RESULTS:

The number of intense Coronary syndrome cases enrolled for our research was one hundred. The age of entire cases in our study was in between fifty-one to sixty-nine years. The number of patients diagnosed with stress hyperglycemia while hospitalization was thirty-nine (thirty-nine percent) as well as the number of cases died during treatment in hospital was twelve (12 percent). The researcher identified statistically important (P value is equal to 0.056) linkage during hospitalization causalities and stress hyperglycemia. The researcher conducted stratification in association with the hospitalized casualty. The number of patients died while research interval was twelve (12 percent) among them eight (66.67 percent) cases had stress hyperglycemia while hospitalization. Among eighty-eight alive cases, the number of victims diagnosed with stress hyperglycemia was thirty-one (35.23 percent). The researcher identified statistically important (p is equal to 0.056) relation between hospitalized casualty and stress hyperglycemia.

Table – I: Mortality and Hyperglycemia Stress Prevalence

Stress Hyperglycemia Prevalence and Mortality Rate		Percentage
Stress Hyperglycemia Prevalence	Yes	39
	No	61
Mortality Rate	Yes	12
	No	88

Table – II: Relation of stress hyperglycemia with in-hospital mortality

Mortality during Hospitalization		Yes	No	Total
Yes	Number	8	31	39
	Percentage	66.67	35.23	39.00
No	Number	4	57	61
	Percentage	33.33	63.64	61.00
Total	Number	12	88	100
	Percentage	12.00	88.00	100.00
P-Value		0.056		

DISCUSSION:

The age of entire cases in our study was in between fifty-one to sixty-nine years. Uniformly Mansour, as well as Bhalli et al, recorded average age of all the acute coronary syndrome victims. A number of researchers have presented that SH should be a general symbol in cases with the Acute coronary syndrome and a significant hazardous element for intrahospital obstacles. However, the decision of finding accurate caesuras point for stress hyperglycemia was still waiting, its expansion in epidemiological research changes from twenty-five to fifty percent of cases hospitalized with the acute coronary syndrome. In our research, diagnosed cases of SH are thirty-nine percent. Modenesi et al recorded SH in (26.4 percent) cases that is less, as compared to our research. According to another research Marfella et al diagnosed SH in twenty-nine percent cases. Similarly, in research by Nordin et al in a retrospective evaluation of cases hospitalized with the Acute coronary syndrome, experienced thirty-eight percent expansion of stress hyperglycemia. Various research presented relation between SH and casualty in common public with the acute coronary syndrome. In a research conducted by Mehta et al, cases with acute myocardial infarction along with ST-segment elevation had a death rate of 6.6 percent within an initial month in control group however in another group with stress hyperglycemia; the casualty rate was fourteen percent. In accordance with research carried out by Cheung et al, the death rate was much greater in the category with mean blood glucose ranges higher or parallel to (144 mg/dl). Suleiman et al conducted his study on seven hundred thirty-five nondiabetic cases with acute myocardial infarction Suleiman et al found an

association in blood sugar range at the time of hospitalization with the huge casualty. Svensson et al presented that cases with blood sugar is higher than or parallel to (120mg/dl) had forty-six percent greater casualty correlate with those cases whose blood sugar range were in between (56 & 119 mg/dl). Several researchers have evaluated the differential influence of stress hyperglycemia on the results of victims with acute coronary syndrome. Particularly, stress hyperglycemia arises to be a great symbol of complications.

Whereas the pathophysiological methodology is not still completely apprehending, there is a number of potential definitions. It is also probable that a higher level of stress is compulsory to produce a higher level of hyperglycemia in cases in absence of DM as compared to those with DM. The advantages of rigid control of blood glucose range in severe cases have been authenticating and added a low ratio of organ disorder and death with the treatment of blood sugar ranges between (80 & 110mg/dl in place of the previous target that was among (180 to 200mg/dl). The advantages like to be associated not only to decrease blood sugar range but also to the anti – inflaming consequences of insulin, which decrease the generation of substance associated with oxidative stress and decrease glucotoxicity.

CONCLUSION:

The finding of our research presented by the researcher identified many ACS cases with stress hyperglycemia. During hospitalization, researcher found a strong connection in between casualties and stress hyperglycemia.

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